

The Turing Way Nominations for OpenUK 2022 Awards.

Submission prepared by Malvika Sharan (The Turing Way project Co-lead, Senior Researcher - The Alan Turing Institute)

Nominee Email* theturingway@gmail.com

Award nominated for (you may nominate for more than one, but each category must be a separate entry)* **Belonging**

This nomination is for *The Turing Way* project represented by project leads, a community manager, a core team of 14 staff and volunteer members, and a community of more than 340 contributors from around the world. *The Turing Way* is an open source and community-led project that aims to open up the potential of data science for everyone. *The Turing Way* champions diversity by challenging traditionally siloed research cultures from every angle and provides a community-driven handbook for conducting research in a way that welcomes and supports a truly diverse group of researchers.

Handbook: Our project brings together a diverse community of researchers, educators, learners, administrators, and stakeholders from within The Alan Turing Institute, across the UK, and internationally. We have collectively written a [web-based book](#) with five guides on Reproducible Research, Project Design, Communication, Collaboration and Ethical Research, as well as a Community Handbook. We seek to provide all the information that researchers need at the start of their projects to ensure that they are conducting data science and AI research that is ethical, inclusive and easy to reproduce in the end.

Community and process: *The Turing Way* is much more than a book: it is a community of practice that promotes a culture of collaboration and belonging among global contributors with a diverse range of domain expertise. As a community-developed resource, the project belongs to the community and is always a work in progress. Shared under an open licence, everyone can freely read, reuse, distribute, modify, and contribute back to the resources. *The Turing Way* has embedded equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) at the very core of its work and has made significant contributions to the wider STEM field on several levels. Resources and content: The content of the project focuses on topics that are fundamentally linked to principles of EDI and belonging. As well as being a guide to reproducible research and scientific communication, *The Turing Way* focuses on collaboration and ethical research. The Guide for Collaboration provides recommendations for researchers on how to build diverse teams and create inclusive workspaces spanning topics from remote working to running inclusive events and participatory co-creation. The Guide to Research Ethics grapples with the realities of ethical research, and shares key principles from Responsible Research and Innovation and Research Integrity, as well as sections on activism and internal policy advocacy.

Collective community efforts: Significantly, *The Turing Way* team hasn't produced these guides by choosing a select group of people to decide what is "best practice" but has provided a working example of team science, using a wide community to define the

standards and expectations the community would like to see in responsible and ethical research practice. This approach has empowered diverse individuals from different backgrounds, identities and lived experiences to express their viewpoints, fairly represent different realities in research and particularly involve voices from communities that are traditionally marginalised in STEM. *The Turing Way* now boasts over 345 contributors, who have collectively written over 260 pages across 62 chapters to date. All collaborations and development processes occur in open, challenging the disconnected and isolated nature of the traditional academic research process. Contributors include researchers, open science practitioners, educators, policymakers and data experts across academia, government and industry, in various domains, at all levels of seniority, representing countries including Australia, Argentina, Brazil, Germany, India, the Netherlands, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Uganda, UK, USA, Venezuela and beyond. Based on web traffic monitoring coupled with references in more than 100 online publications, 30+ citations in peer-reviewed articles and personal testimonials, The Turing Way has thousands of users worldwide in academia, industry, open communities and the public sector. The global reach is also reflected in nearly 3000 monthly users of the book worldwide and 20,000+ cumulative downloads of *The Turing Way* resources from Zenodo.

Impact: As well as developing its thriving and diverse community, The Turing Way has engaged in collaborations and advocacy work to encourage reproducible research and collaborative and inclusive research cultures. As a result of these engagements, we have influenced multiple research communities and Data Science projects, and have been cited by more than 20 peer-reviewed articles and nearly 100 online publications, including a reproducibility report from the European Union, a policy commissioned by the Mayor of London, Goldacre review for modern open working and several world-leading training and research organisation. We have inspired the many knowledge-sharing projects that replicate The Turing Way's practices and formats for online repository and community-led initiatives that include a project from the Office of National Statistics, Genomics England, FAIR Cookbook and several projects within the Turing Institute.

Force for culture change in data science: Recent reports have highlighted how much must change in research culture in the UK and open science worldwide for the ambitions we all share in terms of diversity to be realised. *The Turing Way* is different to other projects focused on diversifying data science in that it has fully embraced the need to change scientific and research culture for the better, to support inclusive research for diverse researchers. *The Turing Way* provides a blueprint for what needs to change, but also evidence of how to co-create meaningful practices through collaboration. Ultimately the project has enabled thousands of contributors to share their vision of what a truly global research culture would look like and has presented that knowledge in an entirely accessible and open format.

Relevant Links:

- Online Book (website): <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/welcome>
- Project repository: <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/the-turing-way>
- Twitter handle: <https://twitter.com/turingway>

- Quarterly reports:
https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/the-turing-way/tree/tps-report-2020/project_management/quarterly_reports
- Impact story:
<https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/impact-stories/changing-culture-data-science>
- Other resources on Zenodo under CC-BY license:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/the-turing-way>
- YouTube channels with project resources and updates:
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCPDxZv5BMzAw0mPobCbMNUA>

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Nominator Mobile number

Please confirm that the Nominee has:

- if an individual they must be resident in the UK for the preceding 12 months
- If a project they must have one or more key contributors to project UK resident in the past 12 months
- if a company or other legal entity it must be a UK company or UK subsidiary of an international company or set up in the UK
- your agreement to 25 or under on 31 July 2022 for young person award

Reference:

- Athena:
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IOjO1VmM20-27UPbqVTZBSbSqYXv7-k_Rbdho754d4U/edit
- Einstein:
https://docs.google.com/document/u/1/d/1LzSWfLPk2uxC9YrVg61H4FgfiHvGCnhTBX-kTGZ1Er4/edit?usp=drive_web&oid=102682705838770934280